

**Sustainable SoluTions FOR
recycling of end-of-life Hydrogen
technologies**

Deliverable D7.1

Project website and socials media

Document Details

Due date	30/04/2021
Actual delivery date	30/04/2021
Lead Contractor	Environment Park
Version	First
Prepared by	Monica Risso
Input from	
Reviewed by	

Document Details

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU - Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	CO - Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)

This project has received funding from the Fuel Cells and Hydrogen 2 Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No 101007216. This Joint Undertaking receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, Hydrogen Europe and Hydrogen Europe research.

**FUEL CELLS AND HYDROGEN
JOINT UNDERTAKING**

Contents

1 Executive Summary	3
2 Website and Social media	3
3 Project repository	6

List of Figures

Figure 1 Project homepage	3
Figure 2 Project scheme within the website	4
Figure 3 BEST4Hy partners within the website	4
Figure 4 BEST4Hy twitter profile	5
Figure 5 BEST4Hy LinkedIn profile	5
Figure 6 Project repository	6

Funded by the
Fuel Cells and
Hydrogen 2 Joint
Undertaking under
grant agreement
No 101007216.

1 Executive Summary

The deliverable is developed under the frame of WP7. The goal of WP7 is disseminating project activities, exploiting properly all results obtained and guaranteeing the project outreach. The document describes the website with some screenshots to illustrate it.

The graphical layout has been designed by professionals assuring an easy and user-friendly navigation experience provided across a wide range of devices (from desktop to smartphones).

2 Website and Social media

A public website and the social media are useful channels to disseminate and communicate about the results of a research project. These channels are fundamental to build a community interested in the project and are important requirements for a public co-financed research project. For BEST4Hy Project, a website with the following URL has been created (see Fig 1). The website contains 5 sections (Project and publications, Consortium, news, Contact, Login) and it is regularly updated with news available for partners to translate. In addition to the institutional website, also partners website are used as well to amplify the impact of the dissemination activities.

<https://best4hy-project.eu/>

Figure 1 Project homepage

The website includes the most important project information: the objectives of the project, the main concept (see Fig. 2), the consortium (see Fig. 3), and all publications from the project. Furthermore, it shows all news and events concerning the project which will be regularly updated.

Funded by the Fuel Cells and Hydrogen 2 Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No 101007216.

PROJECT

Figure 2 Project scheme within the website

Figure 3 BEST4Hy partners within the website

Moreover, dedicated LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/best4hy-project>) and Twitter (<https://twitter.com/best4hy>) profiles have been created as shown in Fig. 4 and 5.

Funded by the Fuel Cells and Hydrogen 2 Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No 101007216.

- Home
- Explore
- Notifications
- Messages
- Bookmarks
- Lists
- Profile**
- More

Figure 4 BEST4Hy twitter profile

Figure 5 BEST4Hy LinkedIn profile

Funded by the Fuel Cells and Hydrogen 2 Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No 101007216.

3 Project repository

Within the project website under the Login section, it is included a private section, accessed via username and password, to be used as repository of BEST4Hy internal working documents, as reference point for the team members. The area is organized in spaces for the different WPs under the supervision of the relevant WPL (Fig 6). These areas should be used for facilitating exchange of information amongst the WP's internal team and the teams of the different WPs interacting for data and results, whilst limiting the number and size of emails.

Figure 6 Project repository

A section will be dedicated to general information for the project, and will be managed by the Project Coordination Team: in this area, the project team will find all the Deliverables of the project, the presentations and minutes of the project meetings (General Assembly and Executive Board) and workshops, and all the terms of reference (Grant Agreement and amendments, Consortium Agreement, Non-disclosure agreements etc) plus any other document of common interest to the project consortium (e.g. calendar GANTT, list of contacts etc).

Funded by the Fuel Cells and Hydrogen 2 Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No 101007216.